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UNION

OFFICE OF ASTRONOMY
FOR DEVELOPMENT

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South African
Astronomical Observatory

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Astronomy is a field that combines science and technology with inspiration and excitement. As such, it can play a pivotal role in facilitating education and human capital development. The skills related to the field of astronomy can also be used to further sustainable development throughout the world.

After the International Year of Astronomy (IYA) in 2009, the IAU was motivated to commit to more ambitious programmes of educating the world to the beauty of the universe and the sense of common humanity that derives from it. This led to the creation of a decadal strategic plan to use astronomy to stimulate development at all levels including primary, secondary and tertiary education, science research and the public understanding of science. This plan was ratified at the IAU General Assembly in Brazil in August 2009.

The Office of Astronomy for Development (OAD) is a global office that is mandated to use astronomy to drive positive developmental change. This office was established through a joint partnership between the International Astronomical Union (IAU) and the South African National Research Foundation (NRF).

After a lengthy international selection process, the IAU chose South Africa as the host country for the OAD and the South African

Astronomical Observatory (SAAO), a facility of the National Research Foundation (NRF) as the host institution. This arrangement was strongly supported by the South African Department of Science and Technology (DST). On the 16th of April 2011, the OAD was officially launched by the South African Minister of Science and Technology, Ms Naledi Pandor, at its current location in Cape Town, South Africa.

The purpose of the OAD is to implement the IAU's Strategic plan 2010 – 2020 "Astronomy for Development". This plan describes the potential of astronomy to contribute to sustainable development. The OAD was established to mobilise the necessary human and financial resources in order to realise the field's scientific, technological and cultural benefits to society.

The OAD is tasked with establishing and strategically coordinating Regional Offices and Language Expertise Centres across the world, as well as initiating, supporting and funding programmes that use Astronomy as a tool to tackle development challenges.

After four years of operation, in February 2015, the OAD was assessed by an externally appointed review panel. The appointed members for the review were Dame Jocelyn Bell Burnell, University of Oxford, United Kingdom, Professor Ron Ekers, CSIRO/Australia Telescope National Facility, Australia and Professor George Ellis, University of Cape Town, South Africa. The committee conducted a week-long evaluation of the OAD and its activities during its first four years of existence.

The overall findings from the review were extremely positive and supportive of the OAD.

The panel strongly supported the continuation of the OAD as a joint project of the IAU and NRF until the IAU General Assembly in 2021. They recommended that the IAU make clear its intention to continue the OAD beyond the period of the 10 year plan currently set to end in 2020.

Fig. 2 The 'Astronomy Wheel' illustrates the connection.

Fig. 1 The United Nations Sustainable Development Goals are a set of goals to end poverty, protect the planet, and ensure prosperity for all as part of a new sustainable development agenda.

The IAU Strategic Plan delineates the features of astronomy that can be used to address sustainable development challenges. The wheel above illustrates how astronomy training equips astronomers with interdisciplinary technological and scientific skills essential for the growth of knowledge economies. In addition, the wheel highlights astronomy's cultural and historical relevance to societies across the world. OAD programmes leverage these features of astronomy by connecting the astronomy community to development challenges where related skills are required, through education and improving social outcomes.

The IAU Strategic Plan emphasises the importance of furthering the Millennium Development Goals (MDGs) in all astronomy-for-development activities. In the global discussion led by the United Nations on development initiatives, the MDGs have been succeeded by the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), which represent the general consensus on key challenges faced by all countries around the world. Furthering the SDGs through astronomy is a key task of the OAD.

A key part of the implementation of the IAU Strategic Plan is performed via the OAD annual Call for Proposals, in which individuals and organisations anywhere in the world are invited to propose projects that relate to astronomy-for-development.

The proposed project should address a problem or challenge related to development and should use astronomy as a tool to address this problem. Projects are encouraged to think about how astronomy could be used to further progress in relation to some UN Sustainable Development Goals. The OAD has identified gaps in the field of astronomy that projects are encouraged to address. For example, there is a lack of material and methods for teaching basic mathematics, statistics, engineering, programming using astronomy, material on cultural aspects of astronomy, and research reviews on what works in projects typically funded by the OAD.

The IAU earmarks approximately €110,000 per year for this open call for project proposals, with individual project grants generally ranging between €500 and €15,000. In the first five cycles of the Call, a total of € 7,460,844 was requested for astronomy-for-development projects. Of the proposals received, the OAD selected 106 projects for funding, granting a total of € 515,364.

More information on the call on the [OAD website](#).

Fig. 3 Projects funded under each task force

The OAD believes that in order for astronomy-for-development activities to be effective, a scientific approach is needed. Evaluation is essential for identifying which projects work best, for whom and under what conditions. Evidence-informed project design and selection ensures that projects build on past lessons, thereby reducing the risk of negative unintended consequences and increasing the probabilities of positive cost-effective impacts.

The OAD Impact Cycle aims to enhance the OAD's project design, selection and delivery systems to support such continual improvement and potential expansion. By determining what works and, importantly, what doesn't work, the OAD can develop a library of evidence on best practice and ensure a positive feedback loop for projects.

At the Project Ideas stage, the OAD would provide guidelines on previous experience and existing research to allow proposers to focus their ideas and build on what has been done. This is followed by Optimisation, in which selected projects are optimised by making their theoretical assumptions and target outcomes explicit and incorporating best practice and evaluation design in their implementation plan.

Where possible, the Evaluation stage applies experimental (i.e. scientific) research designs to obtain valid and publishable measures of impacts, while keeping the implementation as unbureaucratic as possible for the project leaders. The Resources are a continuously

updated library of best practices, that will capture what we learn in previous steps. The evidence will then feed back into the Project Ideas stage to create a positive feedback loop.

The Impact Cycle will feed into a global Knowledge Base both through academic publications on evaluated projects and by providing data to serve the STEM education, outreach, evaluation and development communities. Contributions to the global evidence base on science for development, education, outreach and human capital development provide a platform for ensuring that innovative, high-impact projects inform practice on a larger scale. The cycle generates the high quality evidence needed by policymakers and donors designing large-scale education and human capital development interventions.

More information on the impact cycle, including project design, monitoring and evaluation can be found on the [OAD website](#).

Fig. 4 The impact cycle illustrates a plan for using and building evidence of the best practices in astronomy for development projects.

Fig. 5 Projects are funded each year through an open Call For Proposals. Between 2012 to 2017, over 100 projects were funded by the OAD.

STARLIGHT IN THE UNIVERSITY: ASTROLAB (EXTENDED)

 NIGERIA, RWANDA, ZAMBIA
 Task Force 1 (Universities & Research)

In many countries, there is still a large need for young people to get involved in science studies and research. Astrolab is a low cost research tutorial for universities in need of astronomy infrastructure and curriculum. It uses remote telescopes, accessible over the internet, to teach students the primary steps involved in Astronomy research and the scientific method - observation, image acquisition, processing, data analysis and writing up results. Supported by the OAD, Astrolab has run pilot projects in Nigeria, Rwanda and Zambia.

This project is an extension of Astrolab to three or more universities, with several improvements: all necessary software is open-source and freely available, all activities are extensively documented in step-by-step procedures, and additional instruction given by one of the pilot members.

A Regional Workshop on Astronomy Data Analysis was held in November 2016 at the Copperbelt University in Zambia. A group of 34 undergraduate students learned all the steps of data

analysis, from selecting an eclipsing binary system to be observed with a robotic telescope to the final aperture photometric measurements on CCD images.

LATIN AMERICAN SCHOOL OF OBSERVATIONAL ASTRONOMY

 LATIN AMERICA
 Task Force 1 (Universities & Research)

The Latin American School of Observational Astronomy, ESAOBELA, offers a basic course in Astronomy to students from physics, mathematics and engineering from various Latin American countries. The school is organised jointly by the Instituto Nacional Astrofísica, Óptica y Electrónica (INAOE) and by the Instituto de Astronomía of National Autonomous University of Mexico (UNAM).

During the school, students attended theoretical classes which were supported by practical observations using primarily the one-meter telescope of UNAM's National Astronomical Observatory of Tonantzintla. This year, 24 researchers from INAOE, el Instituto de Astronomía de la UNAM, la Universidad de Guanajuato, el Instituto Politécnico Nacional y la Universidad de Guadalajara delivered courses on the astronomy of position and time, the Sun, spectral classification, photometry, stellar evolution,

optical instrumentation and electronics, interstellar material, the galaxy, extragalactic systems, radio astronomy and non-visible astronomy.

GAZA AMBASSADORS OF MARS

 GAZA
 Task Force 1 (Universities & Research)

Gaza Ambassadors of Mars provided a two week training course focused on spreading astronomical knowledge among the Palestinian youth. Participants were exposed to topics such as observational astronomy, modern astronomy, and received telescope training. It presented an opportunity to help the children discover the world outside Gaza Strip and the universe outside our planet, thus allowing young students to look differently at the Sciences in general, and Astronomy in particular. Events were also organized targeted at the public, such as movies, discussions, experiments, and sky observations.

UPLIFTING THE MOZAMBIKAN ASTRONOMY COMMUNITY

 MOZAMBIQUE
 Task Force 1 (Universities & Research)

Mozambique lacks highly qualified astronomers and astrophysicists as well as a scientific culture in the subject. This project aimed to foster interest in Astronomy/Astrophysics among young university students in Mozambique using a JEDI-style workshop (Joint Exchange Development Initiative). Participants attended a pre-JEDI workshop that focused on how to write code in python and the science packages Numpy, Scipy and Matplotlib. During the JEDI workshop, they developed an Astronomy project to improve their skills in coding, scientific method, research and communication.

JEDI is a concept to enhance development and education via direct transfer of skills and expertise in any specific field. This is

achieved by bringing stakeholders: students, postdocs and staffs together in an informal but intense research environment to tackle unsolved problems.

RADIO ASTRONOMY FOR EDUCATION

 BOTSWANA, GHANA, KENYA, MADAGASCAR, MAURITIUS, MOZAMBIQUE, NAMIBIA, SOUTH AFRICA, TANZANIA, ZAMBIA
 Task Force 1 (Universities & Research)

The Radio Astronomy for Education project aims to support human capacity development in Africa and work toward training the valuable assets needed to reach the ambitious goal of the Square Kilometer Array. It achieves this by providing a complete package to build a teaching radio observatory from scratch. The hardware is hooked to a small foldable antenna so that it can be

brought to any training events. Involving learners and teachers in that thriving adventure is critical as it will satisfy the growing need for competent assets.

Building a teaching radio observatory covers a broad variety of skills spanning from science, technology, engineering and mathematics (STEM). It is thus a perfect multidisciplinary project for science faculties. A teaching radio interferometer project has been constructed at the Botswana International University of Science and Technology and efforts are underway in other countries.

THE FIRST ARAB WINTER SCHOOL FOR ASTROPHYSICS

 MOROCCO
 Task Force 1 (Universities & Research)

The First Arab Winter School of Astrophysics (FAWSA) provided a platform for astrophysics knowledge sharing, triggering collaborations between fellow Arab astrophysicists, and building a strong professional Arab community in the field. This winter school was a starting point in providing fundamental knowledge of astrophysics and data analysis skills to advanced undergraduate and postgraduate students in the Arab world and was an opportunity to expose them to existing research activities in order to establish collaborations between different groups.

The school covered the following fields: Solar System and Exoplanets, Solar Physics, Galactic Astronomy: Stars, Stellar Clusters, Nebulae, SNR and ISM, Extragalactic Astronomy:

Galaxy Formation and Evolution, and Cosmology, Observational Astronomy: HRA, Adaptive Optics, Site Testing, Technical Tools: Python, IDL, iraf, and Virtual Observatory.

HAITI ALL SKY CAMERA

 HAITI
 Task Force 1 (Universities & Research)

The Haiti All-Sky Camera (HASC) project installed a specialized camera in Haiti to view and record the night sky. Students from Université Quisqueya (UNIQ) and Ecole Supérieure d'Infotronique d'Haïti (ESIH) along with students from University of Maryland (UMD) collaborated on code (python programming) to automate the image (data) collection, process the images, inventory the images (build a database of interesting observations), and showcase the results on the web. The collected imagery will also serve as a hook to teach students (and the public) about meteors, constellations, motions of the night sky, light pollution, and other aspects of astronomy.

During northern spring 2016, a one week 1-credit class "Python and Astronomy" was taught at ESIH, instrumental for operating the planned all-sky telescope. The project is being continued in 2017, building on the existing infrastructure in a number of ways. The telescope will be made more portable by using a Raspberry

Pi for the data taking, the astronomy/python curriculum will be expanded and the All Sky camera will be showcase at a number of colleges and high-schools.

AN ASTRONOMY CENTER IN BANGLADESH

 BANGLADESH
 Task Force 2 (Children & Schools)

A pilot astronomy project is developing an Astronomy Outreach Center in Bangladesh, the first of its kind in the country. It will be integrated with local schools and colleges for regular observation and small-scale research. The facility will be used to train local children and their teachers with hands-on observing sessions, in astrophotography, observing of variable stars, etc. This will enhance the children's understanding of the world and convey the scale and beauty of the universe, thus providing a broader perspective on our place in the universe.

ASTRONOMY FOR LITERACY

 SIERRA LEONE
 Task Force 2 (Children & Schools)

Astronomy for Literacy (AFL) is working to enhance literacy, numeracy and other foundational skills among struggling junior secondary school students in Sierra Leone. The project is adapting and developing high quality curriculum resources across literacy, math and science. The goal is to use astronomy-related content to teach foundational reading and numeracy skills, while at the same time igniting an interest in astronomy and teaching in an engaging way the core concepts in astronomy that are part of Sierra Leone's national curriculum for science.

The AFL project has developed detailed, highly structured lesson plans that enable relatively low-skilled teachers with limited subject knowledge to still deliver high quality learning opportunities. To date, AFL has developed and taught a science unit on the universe that teaches students about the structure of the universe, our sun and moon, and our planet. A unit test has also been developed to assess student understanding of these concepts. AFL has also developed and taught a social studies unit on "Views of the Universe", which teaches students about early

understandings of the universe across different cultures, scientific understanding of the universe and the development of certain key technologies.

AFL has also invested in finding appropriate supplementary digital resources, including videos, presentations and other offline content, and has purchased 20 low-cost tablet devices that will allow groups of students to access this content.

SOLAR SYSTEM PLAY

 ARGENTINA
 Task Force 2 (Children & Schools)

This project will develop two different games that allow kids to learn about Planetary Systems. The first one, meant for younger children, consists of a board game based on the voyage of the New Horizons spacecraft. By playing the game, students will

learn basic concepts about the Solar System. The second is a card game that will allow older students to understand more specific information regarding our planetary system, and some basic concepts about planetary formation.

The games will impart important and up-to-date information about the Solar System in an agile, dynamic, and intuitive way.

TOUCHING SPACE – ACCESSIBLE ASTRONOMY EDUCATION

📍 UNITED KINGDOM
 ✓ Task Force 2 (Children & Schools)

This project aimed to bring astronomy to both children and adults with visual impairments and other forms of disability. Through the use of sensory activities designed to provide a different approach to learning, the Touching Space project introduced Astronomy to those who previously would not have been able to interact with such a science.

Touching Space was proposed and run by undergraduate students from the University of Central Lancashire (UCLan) who worked with two local charities – Galloway’s Society for the Blind and Action for Blind People (which is now merged with the RNIB).

The project ran with the guidance and support from external organisations such as the UCLan Physics Society, Aerolite Europe and The Space Collective.

The project met adults with a range of visual impairments for a presentation which had an emphasis on descriptive language, the use of sound such as those recorded during meteor showers and asteroseismology (the sound of stars), and the use of tactile materials. A one day workshop was conducted for 4-17 year olds with varying levels of visual and motor impairment and learning difficulties. Participants could experience four hands on activities as well as visit the planetarium at the UCLan Alston Observatory. The project team also had an exhibit at the 2016 Lancashire Science Festival where students could engage with various space and astronomy activities.

SOLVING PROBLEMS AND COSMIC EXPLORATION (S.P.A.C.E)

📍 SOUTH AFRICA
 ✓ Task Force 2 (Children & Schools)

The Solving Problems and Cosmic Exploration (SPACE) program aimed to develop problem solving skills and stimulate creativity through various challenges presented within an astronomy context. It comprised of workshops, science shows, public busking and games. Some of the topics covered in the science shows were telescopes, the science of living in space, and radiation. Workshops included robotics (using Lego Mindstorm), electronics (using LittleBits) and a telescope card game. The workshops and science shows were offered to schools, the general public and science club members, reaching more than 2500 people.

ASTRONOMY FOR EARTHQUAKE AFFECTED STUDENTS

📍 NEPAL
 ✓ Task Force 2 (Children & Schools)

In 2015, a massive earthquake in Nepal destroyed homes, schools, universities and other buildings. Investment will be required not only to rebuild the infrastructure but also for psychological counseling to ensure that children are able to cope with the trauma and resume with their lives.

The inspirational nature of Astronomy may offer some solace during this time. Astronomy activities were conducted for earthquake affected students in three different places - Gorkha, Nuwakot and Kathmandu. Workshops, including solar observations, were organized for teachers and students.

ASTROBUS-ETHIOPIA

📍 ETHIOPIA
 ✓ Task Force 3 (The Public)

AstroBus-Ethiopia is a mobile astronomy outreach program that was carried out by driving a bus – to different locations in Ethiopia. The project aimed to promote astronomy Education and Public outreach (EPO), and stimulate a culture of scientific thinking through the use of exciting astronomy activities. These

activities include sky watching, public lectures, simple astronomy experiments and others.

The outreach program focused on inspiring students and the general public. Different activities were carried out to create and increase awareness of astronomy and space science. This is an effective approach to reach the general public in a creative and inspiring way for promoting astronomy and igniting scientific curiosity.

ASTRONOMY WITH ALL SENSES

📍 COLOMBIA
 ✓ Task Force 3 (The Public)

‘Astronomy with all senses’ is a traveling exhibition designed for people with physical disadvantages, in order to let them know about astronomy and other space science and inspire them with the wonders of the universe. For people with normal abilities, it highlights the importance of all the senses. The exhibition materials (which fit into a backpack) can be used to run 13 activities organized into three modules: Earth-moon system; Solar System sizes and distances and stars; constellations and Nebulas. A digital handbook for the materials, containing background information on each activity as well as how to use it, is available online in Spanish.

DEVELOPMENT OF ASTRO TOURISM IN SOUTH WEST ASIA

📍 SOUTH WEST ASIA
 ✓ Task Force 3 (The Public)

Astronomical tourism involves tourism at sites of astronomical interest, historical and archaeological sites, modern research organizations (observatories, astronomical institutes), educational centres, space museums, planetariums, etc. It may significantly contribute to tourism due to the growing public interest in science. Astro-tourism requires a tight collaboration between science and tourism, i. e. between astronomical research institutions and individual astronomers on the one hand (as well as amateurs and teachers), and travel agencies and experts in tourism on the other hand. It also concerns the organization of scientific conferences and other events, as in this case a number of astronomers travel to the given country combining astronomy and tourism.

Armenia and neighbouring countries are rich in sites of ancient astronomy, as well as modern research institutions, and may be regarded as centres for astronomical tourism. The project team conducted study visits to astro tourism centres in Uzbekistan, Kazakhstan, Tajikistan, Iran and Georgia. Visits to Scientific Tourism Centres were organized for representatives of travel agencies, tourist guides, journalists. A conference on “Scientific Tourism in the South West Asian Region” brought together the tourism and science communities. Finally, the Byurakan Astrophysical Observatory (BAO) photobooklet has been published to promote the site and a website for “Astro Tourism in South West Asia” has been created to provide information on astro tourism centres, tour packages, travel agencies etc.

THE SKY ON A BIKE

 INDIA
 Task Force 3 (The Public)

'The Sky on a Bike' is an Astronomy outreach programme which introduced the wonders of the night sky to identified groups of economically disadvantaged and poorly educated populations in Indian villages with the aim of creating a scientific temper. The objective was to foster science education and dispel myths, as myths related to celestial events are rampant in many areas of India.

The project used telescopes carried on bicycles, termed as Sky Bikes. These Sky Bikes are designed to be affordable and sturdy so that they can be replicated by anyone. They were set up at locations where the public was gathered. Educators explained the night sky and showed the sky through the telescopes, gave out colorful handouts and enacted street plays. The outreach

sessions focused on education, equality in knowledge, science skills, gender empowerment and equality. They targeted urban and rural villages in and around Delhi, Chennai and in selected villages around Sariska, Rajasthan, all in India.

COMMUNITY DEVELOPMENT AROUND TIMOR OBSERVATORY

 INDONESIA
 Task Force 3 (The Public)

This community development project is developing a symbiosis between a prospective astronomical observatory in Timor, Indonesia, and its surrounding community. The goal is to have thriving villages and a successful observatory. The project consists of: (1) Human Capacity Building with programs on empowering human resources (e.g. public officers training) and strengthening schools (e.g. teachers training); and (2) Managing resources sustainably with programs on fulfilling primary needs (water and energy), through education of STEAM (Science Technology Engineering Arts Mathematics) knowledge and skills.

The project aims to empower the local community with STEAM knowledge and skill, management capability, help them procure clean water and energy source, while at the same time require their understanding and commitment to preserve their natural environment for their sustainability. And for this unique symbiosis with the observatory to function optimally. The project is conducted by astronomers of Institut Teknologi Bandung and community development experts of Indonesian Institute for Energy Economics.

A needs assessment survey was completed and the issues were discussed with the surveyor. A public gathering was held to

introduce the plan for the astronomical observatory, discuss its impact on the local community and the community development project. Meaningful dialogues with local people followed for weeks after the gathering. The training in STEM for teachers and training in office financial management for public officers started well.

This program constitutes the first phase of implementation and will be followed on with further visits, trainings and engagement with the local community.

 TASK FORCE 1 – Universities & Research

PROJECT TITLE: **SUMMER WORKSHOP ON RADIO ASTROPHYSICS**
 LOCATION: Mexico

PROJECT TITLE: **HAITI ALL SKY CAMERA**
 LOCATION: Haiti

PROJECT TITLE: **GUATEMALAN SCHOOL OF ASTROPHYSICS 2017**
 LOCATION: Guatemala

PROJECT TITLE: **WEST AFRICAN INTERNATIONAL SUMMER SCHOOL FOR YOUNG ASTRONOMERS**
 LOCATION: Ghana

PROJECT TITLE: **LATIN AMERICAN SCHOOL OF OBSERVATIONAL ASTRONOMY**
 LOCATION: Mexico

PROJECT TITLE: **ASTRONOMY WINTER SCHOOL IN INDIA**
 LOCATION: India

PROJECT TITLE: **REVITALIZING ASTRONOMY EDUCATION AND RESEARCH IN MYANMAR UNIVERSITIES**
 LOCATION: Myanmar

PROJECT TITLE: **BIG DATA IN ASTRONOMY: A TOOL FOR SOCIAL INNOVATION**
 LOCATION: Mauritius

PROJECT TITLE: **MADAGASCAR ASTRONOMY PYTHON WORKSHOP**
 LOCATION: Madagascar

 TASK FORCE 2 – Children & Schools

PROJECT TITLE: **ACTIVE LEARNING ASTRONOMY FOR SCHOOLS IN HAITI**
 Location: Haiti

PROJECT TITLE: **LOOKING ... UP! ASTRONOMY FOR ALL**
 LOCATION: Greece

PROJECT TITLE: **COSMIC CODE: FIRST CONTACT**
 LOCATION: Mexico

PROJECT TITLE: **ASTRONOMY FOR ALL – AMAZON ASTRO NEPA**
 LOCATION: Brazil

PROJECT TITLE: **COLUMBA-HYPATIA: ASTRONOMY FOR PEACE**
 LOCATION: Cyprus

PROJECT TITLE: **HANDS ON BASIC SPACE SCIENCE TRAINING FOR PRIMARY AND JUNIOR SECONDARY SCHOOL SCIENCE TEACHERS**
 LOCATION: Nigeria

 TASK FORCE 3 – The Public

PROJECT TITLE: **BRAZILIAN NETWORK FOR ASTRONOMICAL NEWS**
 LOCATION: Brazil

PROJECT TITLE: **ASTROBABIES: ASTRONOMY IN EARLY CHILDHOOD**
 LOCATION: Colombia

PROJECT TITLE: **OPEN DESIGN DARK SKY SIMULATOR**
 LOCATION: Global

PROJECT TITLE: **NAVAL HILL PLANETARIUM: CONTEXT-APPROPRIATE CONTENT DEVELOPMENT PROJECT**
 LOCATION: South Africa

PROJECT TITLE: **GAZA ASTRONOMY TECHNO-APPS BOOT CAMP (GAZA AMBASSADORS OF UNIVERSE)**
 LOCATION: Gaza

IAU GENERAL ASSEMBLY 2018

The IAU General Assembly (GA) is a periodic gathering of astronomers worldwide from all fields of astronomy. The next GA will take place from August 20–31, 2018 in Vienna, Austria. The OAD will host a Focus Meeting titled “Astronomy for Development.” This meeting will focus on what development (and thus astronomy-for-development) actually means in a global context, highlighting what has been learned so far. It will be a space for input and engagement with the community. The programme for the meeting will include some key topics such as the new IAU Strategic Plan, the OAD annual call for proposals, interdisciplinary imperatives in astronomy-for-development, evaluating impact of projects, evidence informed project design, synergies between IAU structures, volunteers and volunteer opportunities for IAU members.

IAU members casting their votes in favour of resolutions. (Photo credit: IAU/R. Fienberg)

The latest programme can be found on the [OAD website](#).

ASTRONOMY INCLUSION AND ACCESSIBILITY

OAD post-doctoral researcher, Dr Wanda Diaz-Merced, is an Astronomer who makes use of sonification techniques to conduct her research. She lost her sight as a student at university and was left without a way to do her science. Then she had a revelatory insight: the light curves she could no longer see could be translated into sound. Through sonification, she regained mastery over her work, and now she is advocating for a equal participation in the scientific community focusing in Astronomy. Dr Diaz-Merced leads the AstroSense project, which develops software to analyze astronomical data using multimodal perception. She collaborates with the learners and teachers of the Athlone School for the blind in Cape Town. As the chair of the scientific committee, she organised the first workshop on Astronomy Beyond the Common Senses for Accessibility and Inclusion, that was held in Colombia on October 8.

OAD postdoctoral researcher Dr. Wanda Diaz-Merced working on her sonification techniques.

SPACE AWARENESS WORKSHOP

On October 7, 2017, the OAD and European Space Awareness project organized a workshop on Space Education and Outreach in Addis Ababa, Ethiopia. The workshop brought together stakeholders for an engaged dialogue on using space topics for education and outreach in African countries in order to attract young people to science and technology. Discussions built on the work of the European Union funded Space Awareness project that uses the excitement of space and astronomy to stimulate interest of the youth in science and technology and to kindle a spirit of global citizenship. The discussions were preceded by a teachers' workshop in the morning where local teachers had the opportunity to explore best practices and innovative uses of astronomy and space sciences for education.

His Excellency, the Ethiopian State Minister of Science and Technology, Prof. Afework Kassu launched the workshop which was co-organized by Ethiopian Space Science and Technology Institute (ESSTI) and the Ethiopian Regional Office of Astronomy for Development.

The event was funded through the Space Awareness project which received funding from the European Commission's Horizon 2020 Programme under grant agreement n° 638653

Participants of the Space Awareness Workshop included astronomers, space scientists, educators, students, representatives from African Union Commission and EuroPlanet as well as OAD Regional Offices coordinators from Africa and Arab region. (Photo credit: ESSTI)

ASTROVARSITY

The AstroVARSITY project intends to provide course and tutorial resources for Maths and Physics lecturers at undergraduate level in order to use astronomy to enhance science teaching as well as potentially start an astronomy module within their department. The project also offers hands-on activities and exercises based on an off-the-shelf telescope and instruments package to conduct practical experiments and research.

The pilot project, led by Dr. Sudhanshu Barway and Laure Catala from the South African Astronomical Observatory, targets historically black universities in South Africa that are less developed than their counterparts. Several workshops have been organized since 2012 to train lecturers, present astronomy teaching material, and discuss the format of an introductory course in astronomy. The most recent workshops focused on virtual observatory software and tools to create a conducive platform to produce world class astrophysicists and cosmologists.

The success of these workshops encouraged the University of Zululand to acquire their own astronomical equipment which has increased student interest in Physics and Mathematics at the university.

Project leaders Dr. Sudhanshu Barway (left-front standing) and Laure Catala (middle-centre), with some of the participants.

OAD AT MIDDLE EAST AND AFRICA REGIONAL IAU MEETING (MEARIM IV)

The fourth Middle East and African IAU Regional meeting (MEARIM), was jointly hosted by Entoto Observatory & Research Center (EORC) and East African Regional Office of Astronomy for Development (EA-ROAD) from 22–25 May 2017 in Addis Ababa, Ethiopia with the theme of “Exploring our Universe for the benefit of Humankind”. The aim of the meeting was to strengthen and build capacity of Middle East and African regional development in Astronomy and provide a forum for scientists and students in the region to exchange ideas and experiences.

The meeting was launched by His Excellency Dr. Ing. Getahun Mekuria, the Ethiopian Minister of Science and Technology. In addition to various scientific talks, the meeting included multiple sessions on “Astronomy for Development”.

The meeting was attended by about 120 participants from over 30 countries, including representatives from all of the OAD Regional Offices.

Following the conference, the IAU and the Ethiopian government signed an addendum to the agreement of hosting the regional office in Ethiopia. The signing event was attended by coordinators from all nine OAD Regional Offices (ROADs) and Language Centres (LOADs).

Prof. Piero Benvenuti, General Secretary of the IAU (centre), Mr. Kevin Govender, Director of the Office of Astronomy for Development (left), and His Excellency Dr.-Ing. Getahun Mekuria, the Ethiopian Minister of Science and Technology (right) signing the addendum to the agreement for hosting the East African Regional Office of Astronomy for Development. Also in the picture is Dr Solomon Tessema, Director of ESSTI.

INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCE ON RESEARCH INFRASTRUCTURES

Kevin Govender, the Director of the OAD, delivered the keynote address at the International Conference on Research Infrastructures (ICRI 2016), an international forum encouraging global cooperation and providing a unique opportunity to share views on matters of international relevance in the Research Infrastructures’ domain. ICRI2016 was organized in Cape Town from 3 to 5 October 2016, by the South African Department of Science and Technology and the European Commission.

Research infrastructures are core enablers of competitive research, development and innovation, advancing the frontiers of our knowledge. They are often by nature cross border and exploitable by multiple disciplines. Research Infrastructures are also highly data intensive, with more and more virtually enabled access, leading the way to global exploitation.

The overall objective of ICRI 2016 was to explore the move towards a reinforced cooperation on globally-relevant Research Infrastructures and to discuss concrete steps in this direction.

Kevin Govender, director of the OAD, delivering the keynote speech at ICRI 2016.

WHITE HOUSE FRONTIERS CONFERENCE

In October 2016, OAD post-doctoral researcher, Dr Wanda Diaz, was invited to the White House Frontiers Conference hosted by US President Obama in Pittsburg, USA. Co-hosted with the University of Pittsburgh and Carnegie Mellon University, the conference explored the future of innovation in the US and around the world. Wanda’s speech on Making Space Exploration Accessible to All talked about the need for inclusiveness in Science, including high tech areas such as space exploration and Astronomy.

“I believe that astronomy, and all of the sciences, can inspire, amaze and help us create a better world. That is why I am so excited to be participating in the White House Frontiers Conference – an event that is bringing together hundreds of innovators like me who are reimagining the boundaries of what is possible in order to shape the present and the future. While the term frontier is often thought of in relation to space, it is about more than astronomy, or physics, or any one scientific discipline. It is about innovation and curiosity and exploration. It is about making incredible breakthroughs in health care and personalized medicine, because each of us is different and has something to contribute. It is about pushing the boundaries of data, to develop tools like sonification, yes, and also to create more inclusive communities by solving transportation challenges and expanding education opportunities. It is about harnessing the potential of new technologies like artificial intelligence, robotics, and automation to find out how they can benefit all Americans.”

I think that science is for everyone. It belongs to the people, and it has to be available to everyone, because we are all natural explorers.”

Wanda Diaz-Merced from the OAD speaking at the White House Frontiers Conference.

OAD AT LATIN AMERICAN REGIONAL IAU MEETING (LARIM XV)

The Andean Regional Office of Astronomy for Development (ROAD) organized a workshop on the theme of ‘Astronomy for Development’ at LARIM 2016. The workshop gathered astronomers, students and other stakeholders for a discussion on using astronomy for development and development principles for the Andean region.

The Andean ROAD gathers 20+ institutions in Bolivia, Chile, Colombia, Ecuador, Peru and Venezuela. Its coordinators are hosted at three collaborating institutions: Universidad de Los Andes (Colombia), Parque Explora-Planetario de Medellín (Colombia), and Sociedad Chilena de Astronomía (Chile).

A workshop on Astronomy Inclusion was held in conjunction with the LARIM meeting, organized by the IAU Working Group on Astronomy for Equity and Inclusion. It was attended by educators, astronomers and other experts in inclusive education.

The Latin American Regional IAU Meeting was held in Cartagena de Indias, Colombia in October 2016.

Workshop on Astronomy for Development at LARIM 2016.

The OAD team is based out of its office at the South African Astronomical Observatory in Cape Town. While the core team is small, we have a number of interns and fellows working with us throughout the year, contributing in various ways. We are also indebted to the staff at the SAAO who assist us on a daily basis, the Regional Offices, Task Forces, the Steering Committee members, other partners and collaborators, and various volunteers.

This section lists the staff of the OAD and interns, fellows at the office in 2017:

STAFF

KEVIN GOVENDER
Director

NUHAAH SOLOMON
Admin Officer

VANESSA MCBRIDE
Astronomer

ELI GRANT
International Projects Coordinator

POST DOCTORAL RESEARCHERS

WANDA DIAZ-MERCED
Post-doctoral researcher

PIERRE-YVES LABLANCHE
Post-doctoral researcher

CURRENT AND PAST INTERNS/FELLOWS

RAMASAMY VENUGOPAL
Visiting Fellow

KARABO MAKOLA
DST Intern, May 2016 – Jun 2017

MUNIRA HOOSAIN
Intern, Dec 2016

JACK HARVEY
Intern, Jan – Apr 2017

EUAN BRODERICK
Intern, Jun – Jul 2017

PAUL A. WILSON
Visiting Fellow, Mar – Aug 2017

ANNIKA MÜLLER
Intern, Aug – Sep 2017

MELO MTOMBENI
Intern, Nov – Dec 2017

The Regional Offices of Astronomy for Development (ROAD) are similar to the OAD, established within host institutions and employing a full time coordinator, with a focus on activities in a specific geographic region. Language Centres or LOADs have a similar structure but with a focus on a particular language or cultural region, which sometimes stretches across the entire world. The OAD has nine Regional Offices - eight ROADs (East Asia, South East Asia, East Africa, Southern Africa, West Africa, the Andean Region of South America, South West Asia, and the Arab world) and three LOADs (Chinese, Portuguese and Arabic languages and cultures). These offices, in addition to providing guidance and support to the OAD on regional matters, drive various activities in their respective regions. The following is the summarized information of the OAD regional offices:

ANDEAN REGIONAL OFFICE OF ASTRONOMY FOR DEVELOPMENT

HOST COUNTRY – Colombia and Chile
HOST INSTITUTION – Universidad de Los Andes, Parque Explora-Planetario de Medellín and Sociedad Chilena de Astronomía
COUNTRIES UNDER THE OFFICE – Colombia, Chile, Bolivia, Ecuador, Peru, Venezuela
CO-ORDINATORS – Germán Chaparro, Farid Char, Jaime Forero, Angela Pérez

ARAB REGIONAL OFFICE OF ASTRONOMY FOR DEVELOPMENT AND ARABIC LANGUAGE EXPERTISE CENTRE

HOST COUNTRY – Jordan
HOST INSTITUTION – Arab Union for Astronomy and Space Sciences, United Nations Regional Centre for Space Science and Technology Education
COUNTRIES UNDER THE OFFICE – Kingdom of Saudi Arabia (KSA), Jordan, United Arab Emirates (UAE), Bahrain, Tunisia, Algeria, Comoros, Djibouti, Sudan, Syria, Somalia, Iraq, Oman, Palestinian Authority, Qatar, Kuwait, Lebanon, Libya, Egypt, Morocco, Mauritania and Yemen
CO-ORDINATOR – Awni Al-Khasawneh

EAST ASIAN REGIONAL OFFICE OF ASTRONOMY FOR DEVELOPMENT AND CHINESE LANGUAGE EXPERTISE CENTRE

HOST COUNTRY – China
HOST INSTITUTION – Xi'an Jiaotong-Liverpool University (XJTLU), Beijing Planetarium and Yunnan Astronomical Observatory
COUNTRIES UNDER THE OFFICE – People's Republic of China, Mongolia, Democratic People's Republic of Korea
CO-ORDINATOR – Thijs Kouwenhoven (EA-ROAD co-director), Ziping Zhang (EA-ROAD co-director), Jun Lin (Chinese Language Center)

EAST AFRICAN REGIONAL OFFICE OF ASTRONOMY FOR DEVELOPMENT

HOST COUNTRY – Ethiopia
HOST INSTITUTION – Ethiopian Ministry of Science and Technology, Ministry of Education, The Ethiopian Space Science Society, and Addis Ababa University
COUNTRIES UNDER THE OFFICE – Ethiopia, Burundi, Comoros, Djibouti, Democratic Republic of Congo, Eritrea, Kenya, Rwanda, Uganda, Somalia, Sudan, South Sudan, Seychelles, Tanzania
CO-ORDINATOR – Alemiye Mamo

PORTUGUESE LANGUAGE OFFICE OF ASTRONOMY FOR DEVELOPMENT

HOST COUNTRY – Portugal
HOST INSTITUTION – Núcleo Interativo de Astronomia (NUCLIO), in collaboration with the Institute of Astrophysics and Space Sciences
COUNTRIES UNDER THE OFFICE – All Portuguese speaking countries including Portugal, Angola, Brazil, Cape Verde, Equatorial Guinea, Mozambique, Guinea-Bissau, Macau, Sao Tome and Principe, East Timor
CO-ORDINATOR – Sara Anjos

SOUTH EAST ASIAN REGIONAL OFFICE OF ASTRONOMY FOR DEVELOPMENT

HOST COUNTRY – Thailand
HOST INSTITUTION – National Astronomy Research Institute of Thailand (NARIT)
COUNTRIES UNDER THE OFFICE – Thailand, Brunei, Cambodia, Indonesia, Laos PDR, Malaysia, Myanmar, The Philippines, Singapore, Vietnam
CO-ORDINATORS – Wichan Insiri, Supaluck Chanthawan, Sulisa Chariyalertsak, Setthawut Thongmee

SOUTH WEST AND CENTRAL ASIAN REGIONAL OFFICE OF ASTRONOMY FOR DEVELOPMENT

HOST COUNTRY – Armenia
HOST INSTITUTION – Byurakan Astrophysical Observatory (BAO)
COUNTRIES UNDER THE OFFICE – Armenia, Georgia, Iran, Kazakhstan, Tajikistan
CO-ORDINATORS – Areg Mickaelian (Director of SWCA ROAD, Armenia), Maya Todua (Georgia), Habib Khosroshahi (Iran), Rashit Valiullin (Kazakhstan), Gulchehra Kohirova (Tajikistan)

SOUTHERN AFRICAN REGIONAL OFFICE OF ASTRONOMY FOR DEVELOPMENT

HOST COUNTRY – Zambia
HOST INSTITUTION – Copperbelt University
COUNTRIES UNDER THE OFFICE – Zambia, Botswana, Lesotho, Namibia, South Africa, Swaziland, Zimbabwe, Mozambique, Malawi, Madagascar, Mauritius, Ghana.
CO-ORDINATORS – Prosperity Simpemba, Lenganji Mubanga Mutembo

WEST AFRICAN REGIONAL OFFICE OF ASTRONOMY FOR DEVELOPMENT

HOST COUNTRY – Nigeria
HOST INSTITUTION – Centre for Basic Space Science (CBSS), National Space Research and Development Agency (NASRDA) at the University of Nigeria
COUNTRIES UNDER THE OFFICE – Nigeria, Benin, Burkina Faso, Cape Verde, Gambia, Ghana, Guinea, Guinea Bissau, Liberia, Mali, Mauritania, Niger, Senegal, Sierra Leone, Togo, Saint Helena, Ivory Coast, São Tomé and Príncipe
CO-ORDINATOR – Bonaventure Okere

Fig. 6 OAD Regional offices across the world

There are many ways to engage with the OAD. We welcome your ideas and input towards the vision of Astronomy for Development. The bulk of the implementation of projects is carried out by volunteers, supported by the OAD and the ROADs/LOADs, with advice and guidance from the Task Forces, and oversight by an international Steering Committee.

The greatest resource enabling the OAD to achieve its vision is therefore its volunteer community. Assistance is sought on an ongoing basis from professionals, amateurs, educators, students or members of the public anywhere in the world. There is an active call on the OAD website for volunteers to register their skills, preferred target regions and interests so that

the OAD can match volunteers with opportunities. There is also a call for organisations or projects to submit requests for volunteers, with the OAD facilitating the volunteer matching process. The OAD currently has over 500 volunteers who are regularly called upon to engage and support various projects and activities.

The OAD has established several partnerships and collaborates with organisations sharing common interests. These partnerships include visiting scientist programmes, funding of workshops, scholarships, joint funding proposals, sharing of expertise and provision of staff time.

Below are some of the organizations that the OAD has partnered with historically.

CALL TO ACTION

PERFORM RESEARCH AT OAD

PARTNER WITH OAD

VOLUNTEER / REQUEST A VOLUNTEER

BECOME AN OAD INTERN OR FELLOW

ADOPT A PROJECT

SET UP A REGIONAL OFFICE

PROPOSE A PROJECT

FUND A PROJECT

Volunteering with the OAD offers opportunities to make new friends and develop international collaborations; travel; develop new skills; learn about science for development and policy research; publish in peer-reviewed journals; be recognised for your contributions; and, most of all, use your time and energy to make a difference.

IMPRINT

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